

ISSUES OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF CREATION OF CHAINS OF ADDED VALUE IN AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTION

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Annotation.

The article analyzes the possibility of processing raw materials grown by the cluster method, delivering them to the consumer in the form of finished products.

Key words: cluster, agriculture, value chain, horticulture, viticulture, market mechanisms, processing, export.

In the conditions of economic liberalization, the current state of the production of fruit and vegetable products and its changes are not only the issues of food supply to the population, the direct and indirect impact of the supply of essential raw materials of the industrial sector on the growth of the real sector of the economy and contribute to the development of the

In recent years, consistent measures are being taken to reform agriculture and introduce market forces into the sector.

In particular, in agriculture, a cluster method of production has been established, the size of the agricultural areas allocated to clusters is made up of cotton-textile – 67 percent, in livestock – 8 percent, in fruit-vegetable – 7,5 foizni.

The processing of raw materials grown by the cluster method allows it to be delivered to the consumer in the form of a finished product.

Today, more than 80 kinds of agricultural products grown in the Republic are exported to 66 countries of the world. In 2010, when 11,3 percent of exports accounted for cotton fiber, by 2018 this figure decreased to 1,6 percent.

At the same time, the fact that effective marketplaces are not structurally established in the field, especially in the development of fruit and vegetable growing and viticulture, insufficient scientific approach leads to the fact that the existing opportunities of the network are not fully utilized.

According to the calculations, in relation to cotton raw materials grown on an area of 1 hectare, there is an opportunity to earn 7 times more than grapes, 6 times more than cherries, 5 times more than nuts.

In order to ensure the implementation of the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on approval of the strategy of the development of Agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030" dated October 23,

2019, № PF-5853, to produce high-value-added products in the field of fruit and vegetables and viticulture, to increase the volume of exports, to:

Decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan on measures to ensure more effective organization of the process of acquisition of rights over land parcels and other immovable property as part of the South Caucasus pipeline expansion project more ...

According to the resolution of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 14, 2019 "on measures for the development of agricultural cooperation in the field of fruit and vegetable"PP-4239:

In 8 districts of Jizzakh, Samarkand, Tashkent and Fergana regions, a total of 41 fruit and vegetable agricultural associations have been established;

In order to ensure the employment of low-income families by the Ministry of employment and Labor Relations of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Council of farmer, peasant farms and landowners of Uzbekistan attracted the funds of international financial institutions in order to ensure the employment of low-income families, it was determined that in 2020 in 22 districts of Fergana, Andijan and Namangan

In the document, the Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Ministry of Economy and industry, the Ministry of employment and Labor Relations, the Council of farmers, peasant farms and landowners of Uzbekistan issued an agreement on the introduction of new measures for the development of the cluster and cooperative system in the cultivation, processing and export of fruits and vegetables and grapes.

The introduction of such a procedure is envisaged in accordance with it:

- the organization of clusters for the cultivation, processing and export of fruit and vegetable and grape products (in subsequent places-fruit and vegetable clusters) is carried out on the basis of the initiative, duly the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Karakalpakstan and the regional authorities, as well as the trilateral agreement between the Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan (in;
- the initiators of the organization of the fruit and vegetable cluster, as a rule, are selected from among the processing and exporting organizations, based on their experience and capabilities, in the first place it is envisaged to start up completely unused capacities for storage and processing of products;
- the attachment of fruit and vegetable and grape growers to fruit and vegetable clusters is carried out by means of agreements on the supply of products

concluded on the basis of volunteerism between the processing and exporting organizations and the district municipality with them;

- participants of the fruit and vegetable cluster – the relationship between the organizations that grow, process and export products is regulated by the agreements on the supply of products;

- product delivery agreements shall be concluded on the basis of the decisions on the placement of fruit and vegetable and grape products adopted by the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Karakalpakstan and the khokims of the regions on the basis of proposals of processing and exporting organizations, and on the terms of the Tripartite Agreement and shall be registered by the;

- product delivery contracts are concluded on the basis of the requirements of civil legislation, including the determination of the price of the product based on the actual cost, the provision of product growers with seeds, seedlings, mineral fertilizers, side-lubricants and other resources, the provision of agrotechnics and agrochemistry services, the provision of recommendations for the application of new innovative technologies, the provision of.

It was determined that within a month the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Karakalpakstan and the regional authorities, together with the Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the state agency for land resources, Geodesy, cartography and state cadastre, will conduct a complete survey of the existing garden vineyards in all 55 districts specializing in fruit and vegetable production. According to the results of the conducted correspondence, it was determined that the formation and approval of address lists for the renewal of unproductive garden vineyards in each district section, bunda envisages the renewal of unsuitable garden vineyards for 2020 year, and in 2021-2025-low-yield, obsolete and inefficient garden vineyards.

When restoring fresh garden vineyards, it is necessary to ensure that they are attached in advance to a certain cluster of fruits and vegetables or to an agricultural association, provided for its economic efficiency.

In the document, the Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the agency for the development of horticulture and greenhouse economy, the agency for the development of viticulture and winemaking, as well as the Council of farmers, peasant farms and landowners of Uzbekistan open land areas not used in Agriculture, cotton and grain fields with low yields, as well as intensive restoration of, issuance through commercial banks and leasing companies are later defined to organize work on the basis of which they establish agricultural associations and clusters of fruits and vegetables.

In the decision, the promotion of cooperative relations between members of agricultural associations and participants of fruit and vegetable clusters is carried out through their financial support, the provision of working capital through processing and exporting organizations, which are participants in the tripartite agreement of producers of bunda products, the restoration of new gardens, vineyards and greenhouses, in order to create objects of storage and processing of products, up to 20 billion soums of loans allocated by commercial banks are provided with compensation or a guarantee in the amount of 50 percent of the loan amount, which exceeds the refinancing rate of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan, but not more than 8 percent of the interest rate

At present, even in farmer farms specializing in viticulture, great attention is paid to the repair of vineyards, replenishing them with fresh grape varieties.

In allocating loans for these projects to commercial banks involved in financing projects of intensive garden vineyards establishment, it was recommended to introduce the procedure for setting a grace period on the principal loan until the garden vineyards yield (by type).

In the decision, the Ministry of investments and foreign trade of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Ministry of Agriculture together with commercial banks: funds of international financial institutions are widely attracted to support the system of cultivation, processing and export of fruits and vegetables and grapes. It is noted that the attracted funds of international financial institutions will be provided to producers, processing and exporting organizations of products in the Republic of Karakalpakstan and regions.

In this document, from the account of the fund for the development of horticulture and greenhouse economy under the agency for the development of horticulture and greenhouse economy under the Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as the fund for the support of grape growers and wine growers of the agency for the development of viticulture and vinochs – members of agricultural associations and participants of fruit and vegetable clusters will be allocated subsidies to cover part of the cost of purchasing intensive seedlings (pakana and semi-pakana) grown locally, as well as payvandtes.

From the account of the fund for support of grape growers and wine-makers of the agency for development of viticulture and vinochilikni under the Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan – a guarantee on loans allocated by

commercial banks for financing investment projects in the direction of viticulture is provided.

From the account of the state fund for Employment Promotion under the Ministry of employment and Labor Relations of the Republic of Uzbekistan – it is allowed to allocate subsidies to members of agricultural associations established in order to ensure employment of low-income families.

The Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Ministry of employment and labor relations and the Ministry of Finance, together with the Ministry of Finance, have been instructed to introduce proposals to the Cabinet of Ministers on amendments and additions to government decisions regulating the activities of these funds in order to determine the exact nature of the allocation of the

In the resolution, proposals are made on the application of the "zero" rate of rent payment for five years to the areas occupied by the State Department of Forestry of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2020-2021 newly restored and rented Walnut-fruit gardens (pistachio, almond, walnut) on the undeveloped land plots of the forest fund.

The State Department of Forestry of the Republic of Uzbekistan has been instructed to establish new walnut-fruit gardens and to identify entrepreneurs for the development, financing and implementation of investment projects for the cultivation of pistachios, almonds, walnut products, to take measures to assist them in the use of the types of benefits and financial assistance provided for by the legislation.

In addition, the application of additional financial support provided for in this decision for information does not exclude the financial support of product growers, processing and exporting organizations from the accounts of other sources, including funds under the state budget, ministries and departments of the Republic of Uzbekistan and family entrepreneurship support programs, in accordance with the procedure established by the legislation.

Ministry of investments and foreign trade of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Ministry of Foreign Affairs, Ministry of Agriculture, Ministry of transport," Uzstandard " agency, state agency for quarantine of plants under the Cabinet of Ministers," Uzagrokimyohimoya " JSC," Uzkimyosanoat " JSC:

a) "road map" has been developed and approved in order to expand the geography of exports of fruits and vegetables and grape products, reduce tariffs and notaries in exports within a month. It provides for the following::

increasing exports to non-traditional markets, especially China, Korea, India, EU countries for the types of fruit and vegetable and grape products;
negotiations with the competent authorities of foreign countries on granting privileges and discounts on the application of import duties and excise rates;
reduction of payments levied on the transportation of goods by rail, automobile and air;
to increase the production of products in accordance with the requirements of internationally recognized standards, to expand the coverage of processing and exporting organizations on the basis of the requirements of these standards of fruit and vegetable and grape products, to accelerate the certification of export-oriented products on the basis of international requirements;
import of seeds and seedlings without a certificate of "Health" and stop planting;
establish an effective system for the sale of mineral fertilizers and fight against pests in the districts specializing in fruit and vegetable production, ensuring compliance with environmental safety requirements in their activities;
b) information submitted to the administration of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Cabinet of Ministers until December 1, 2020 on the work carried out.

Experience starting from 2020 1 janvar:

- to determine the volume of products grown in the placement of fruit and vegetable and grape varieties in the relevant region on the basis of the normative yield (in subsequent places – normative yield) calculated in relation to one bonitet score of the soils of gardens and vineyards;
- compliance with regulatory productivity requirements by product growers with the help of contracts concluded with their participation, State Statistics reports and information systems of authorized bodies, monitoring by regional agricultural bodies;
- to discuss the results of the monitoring at least once a year in the District Councils of people's deputies.

On the basis of summarizing the results of the conducted monitoring, until March 1, 2021, the Cabinet of Ministers was instructed to introduce proposals on the implementation of effective measures in accordance with the decisions of the District Councils of people's deputies in relation to the owners of land plots that are inefficient use of land plots.

The decision includes: the minister of Agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan together with the chairman of the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Karakalpakstan and the governors of the regions – it was determined to

specialize 55 districts specialized in fruit and vegetable production into a separate type of product, to effectively organize the activities of agricultural associations and fruit and vegetable clusters operating in the direction of fruit and vegetable production, as well as to establish cherry, walnut and peach in 8 thousand hectares, apricot and pomegranate in 8 thousand hectares and plum

The minister of employment and Labor Relations of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the chairman of the board of farmer, peasant farms and landowners of Uzbekistan – the minister of investments and foreign trade of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the effective implementation of the activities of agricultural associations established in order to ensure the employment of low-income families, for the effective use of – to attract funds of international financial institutions for the financing of the system of cultivation, processing and export of fruit and vegetable and grape products, effective organization of the system of state support of organizations that export and provide services to them, chairman of the State Department of Forestry of the Republic of Uzbekistan – Organization of fruit orchards with nuts, expansion of the volume of cultivation and export of products such as pistachios, almonds and nuts, director of the agency for the development of horticulture and greenhouses under the Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan, director of the agency for the development of viticulture and vinochilikni – restoration of new intensive garden vineyards on lands with unsuitable gardens, greenhouses and vineyards, construction of greenhouses, Organization of agricultural associations and clusters of fruits and vegetables on the basis of the fields of crops, which were later rented in one territory, the place of the minister of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan – providing the state fund with the necessary financial resources to support – ninety-nine methods of cultivation and timely cultivation of fairytale crops, in which the full cultivation of products of the specified type and size was established.

The adoption of government decisions on the adoption of measures for the targeted support of the activities of fruit and vegetable clusters established in 2020, the regulation on the procedure for the restoration of intensive garden vineyards, construction of greenhouses and their issuance to the population on the basis of leasing and credit conditions, the regulation on the procedure for finding garden vineyards

In the place of the conclusion, it should be noted that the implementation of the above measures envisaged in the state program for the development of value-added chains in agricultural production ensures the delivery of fruit and

vegetable products abroad in high quality. In addition, it is urgent to develop the activities of the rural infrastructure and the institutions included in it, as well as to further revitalize its functions related to the agro-industrial complexes. The agricultural output of the subjects of the market and production infrastructure should formulate their interaction with the growers.

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